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Advancing the use of digital health technologies for older adults self-managing at home with multimorbidity

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Abstract

Multimorbidity has become an increasingly significant public health concern globally due to its increasing prevalence, particularly within older adult populations. For persons with multimorbidity, self-management of conditions at home is challenging. The SEURO project aims to evaluate via an effectiveness implementation hybrid trial (EIH) across 3 EU countries a novel digital health solution (PROACT) to enhance self-management practices and care for older adults living with multimorbidity.

Introduction

Multimorbidity, defined as the coexistence of two or more chronic conditions in an individual, has a global prevalence of 37.2%, affecting over half of adults over 60 (Chowdhury et al., 2023). Services for persons with multimorbidity (PwMs) are often poorly integrated, leading to inefficiencies, burdens, and potential safety risks, significantly affecting their quality of life (Ploeg et al., 2017; Eckerblad et al., 2015). There is a need to improve best practice around self-management and care for PwMs.

Funded across two European Commission Horizon 2020 projects (ProACT² and SEURO³), PROACT is a digital health platform co-designed with end-users to enhance self-management and care for older PwMs (65 years and over). The platform includes a tailored self-management application paired with a selection of devices to monitor health indicators such as blood pressure, blood glucose, and oxygen levels and well-being parameters like activity and sleep. This allows for personalised tracking, enabling PwMs to make informed decisions about their self-management and care through training and education tailored to their conditions.

Initially evaluated as part of the ProACT project (2016-2019) with n=120 PwMs across Ireland and Belgium (n=60 per region) in a longitudinal action research study (Dinsmore et al., 2021), outcomes show the majority of participants sustained engagement with the solution due to its usability and triage support, experiencing multiple benefits including improved self-management and well-being (Doyle et al., 2021; Sheng et al., 2023). The follow up SEURO project (2021-2025) will advance the platform and evaluate its effectiveness at scale across 3 EU countries.

² <https://proact2020.eu>

³ <https://seuro2020.eu>

Methods

SEURO will employ a Type 1 Effectiveness Implementation Hybrid (EIH) trial design with n=720 PwMs across Ireland, Belgium and Sweden (n=240 per country)⁴. The EIH trial consists of a 3 arm (n=80 per arm per region) pragmatic Randomised Controlled Trial (pRCT) with embedded mixed-methods process evaluation (Curran et al., 2012). PwMs will be aged 65 and older, with two or more of the following conditions: diabetes; chronic respiratory disease; chronic heart failure; and/or chronic heart disease. Participants will be randomised (unblinded) to one of the three trial arms (**Arm 1:** Customised PROACT CareApp and devices + clinical triage support (observational only); **Arm 2:** Non-customised PROACT CareApp and devices; **Arm 3:** No technology/continue with their current self-management routine). Primary outcomes will focus on perceived quality of life and healthcare utilisation, whilst the secondary outcomes will explore PwMs' self-management of conditions across arms. The trials will not examine clinical effectiveness in terms of diagnosis or treatment etc.

Results and Discussion

Results will be reported upon the completion of the SEURO EIH trial in May 2025. Primary outcomes will assess the potential impact on PwMs and the health service, including cost-effectiveness. Secondary outcomes will explore how the platform influences patient engagement with self-management practices.

Conclusion

The PROACT platform marks a major advancement in digital health technologies designed to support older PwMs. It has the potential to significantly improve health outcomes and enhance the quality of life for this vulnerable population. The effectiveness of the platform will be evaluated through the SEURO EIH trial.

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⁴ ISRCTN34134007 Trial Registration: <https://doi.org/10.1186/ISRCTN34134007>

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